

Deep water and lowland rice germplasm collection and evaluation in North Bihar

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North Bihar has more than 2 million ha of rice, 80% of which is grown in poorly drained and deep water areas. We began collecting germplasm from those areas in 1978 and have identified 350 varieties: 90 deep water rices and 260 lowland rices. All varieties identified, except intermediate TCA20-1, 20-2, 212, and 217, were tall. Some were evaluated for yield, yield characters, and drought tolerance.

Three deep water environments were identified, based on water depth: medium deep water (about 1 m); deep water (up to 2 m); and very deep water (4-5 m). Twenty very deep water varieties were identified.

Deep water rices had longer panicles with more grains per panicle than lowland varieties. Very deep water rices had the most grains per panicle (140-324). Lowland rices had 72-164 grains per panicle.

Drought can be a problem in these areas. In Mar 1979, 65 varieties were direct-seeded in deep water tanks. There was a severe drought in May-Jun and many entries died. TCA2, 4, 7, 8 (deep water varieties), and TCA9, 13, 14, 16, 20, 21, 26, 30, 35, and 38 had drought resistance.

Promising deep water and lowland cultures, North Bihar, India.

Collection no.	Grain color	Kernel color	Elongation	Suitability	Additional information
TCA4	Straw	Red	Better	D. W.	BB resistant
TCA11	Straw	Red	Better	D. W.	BB resistant
TCA176	Black	Red	Better	D. W.	
TCA177	Black	Red	Best	D. W.	BB resistant
TCA191-1	Black	Red	Best	D. W.	
TCA20-1	Straw	White	Better	D. W.	
TCA55	Straw	White		M. D.	Wider adaptability
TCA78	Black	Red	Good	M. D.	
TCA162	Gold	White	Better	M. D.	Long glume
TCA179-3	Black	Red	Better	M. D.	
TCA21/TCA22	Straw	Red	Good	S. D.	Sturdy stem
TCA43	Straw	White		S. D.	
TCA47	Gold	White		S. D.	
TCA148-3	White	White		S. D.	
TCA127	Gold	Red	Good	S. D.	
TCA48	Gold	White		S. D.	
TCA49	Black	Red		S. D.	
TCA72	Straw	Red		S. D.	
TCA83	Straw	Red		S. D.	Wider adaptability
TCA20-2	Straw	White	Poor	S. D. & L. L.	Sturdy stem
TCA20-3	Straw	White	Poor	S. D. & L. L.	Sturdy stem
TCA190-1	Black	White	Poor	L. L. & S. D.	RTV resistant scented
TCA58	Straw	Red		L. L.	Wider adaptability
TCA108/TCA149	Straw	Red/White	Poor	L. L.	Wider adaptability
TCA212	Straw	White	Poor	L. L.	
TCA227	Brown	White	Poor	L. L.	

^a D. W. = deep water, M. D. = medium deep, S. D. = shallow deep, and L. L. = lowland. BB = bacterial blight, RTV = tungro.

In 1979 and 1980, the varieties were entered in yield nurseries. Twenty-six cultures were identified as promising and entered in multilocation tests (see table). TCA47 and TCA148-3 yielded 3.1 t/ha in shallow or medium deep water.

TCA177 yielded best in deep water and Barogar 5 and Barogar 6 yielded best in medium deep water — about 2.7 t/ha. Varieties tended to yield best under the water regimes from which they were collected. □

NC492, a promising rice for waterlogged fields in West Bengal

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We evaluated 18 elite rice cultures for growth and yield attributes in waterlogged fields (see figure) in the Gangetic Plains of West Bengal in kharif. Eight varieties had better than 70% survival (see table). Days to 50% flowering ranged from 118 to 150. OR330-40-3 flowered earliest and CR292-5258 and CR292-7050 flowered last.

Total dry matter production varied widely. BIET807 accumulated 1,308 g

Changes in rainfall and water depth in the experimental field in 1983 kharif, Calcutta, India.

dry weight/m² and PLA1100, 242 g. Survival percentage appeared to substantially influence dry matter production,

irrespective of days to flowering or maturity. Tilakkachari produced 255 panicles/m², followed by NC492 with

Survival, growth, yield, and yield attributes of rice varieties grown under waterlogged conditions, Calcutta, India.

Variety	Survival (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Days to 50% flowering	Dry matter production (g/m ²)	Panicles/m ²	Spikelets (10 ³ /m ²)	Grains (10 ³ /m ²)	1,000-grain wt (g)
OR143-7	36	2.0	141	766	117	15	12	27
OR117-215	17	2.2	132	600	50	12	10	21
OR330-40-3	80	2.2	118	758	154	17	14	21
Janaki	87	2.1	122	875	200	15	13	21
BIET724	70	3.1	135	1002	172	20	15	26
BIET807	80	3.6	125	1308	200	23	18	24
BIET821	34	2.0	128	725	119	17	11	24
CR292-5258	31	2.2	150	489	144	20	15	18
CR292-7050	21	2.0	150	466	69	8	7	30
CR221-1030	87	3.5	134	792	182	22	19	22
CN499-160-2-1	29	2.2	134	617	126	12	9	18
CN499-160-13-6	83	2.1	135	608	200	21	17	17
CN505-5-32-9	12	1.2	140	325	50	11	8	20
CN506-147-2-1	93	2.4	142	880	200	19	15	25
CN506-147-14-2	14	3.3	135	685	90	19	16	23
PLA1100	12	0.8	144	242	27	7	5	20
NC492	90	4.9	130	1116	253	21	19	31
Tilakkachari	93	3.8	132	1205	255	25	17	26
Mean	53.8	2.5	134.8	747.7	144.9	16.99	13.4	23.02
CD at 5% P	21	0.6	4	200	52	3	3	3

253 panicles. Tilakkachari also produced the maximum spikelets. NC492 yielded highest with 4.9 t/ha, and PLA1100 lowest with 0.80 t/ha. NC492 had high total dry matter, high panicle number, the highest 1,000-grain weight, and high survival percentage. Survival of plants under waterlogged situation is the prime criterion for plant establishment and subsequent manifestation of yield potential. □

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Selection criteria for an F₄ population of a deep water rice cross

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At CRRI we crossed Pankaj, a high yielding semidwarf, with Nagaribao, a traditional deep water rice, to develop high yield deep water lines. Based on their performance, 817 F₃ lines were selected and planted in kharif in inter-

mediate 15-50 cm water depth. Fifty-two plants of each line were planted at 20- × 25-cm spacing, giving an F₄ population of 42,484 plants. The parents also were grown. Deep water killed 1,285 plants in the F₄ population and very wide growth variation was observed among and within lines. Variation was less within lines than between lines.

From 245 lines we selected 980 plants with high vigor; thick to medium-thick culms; compact tillering; rapid internode elongation; nodal rooting; small erect leaves; medium to tall height; lodging

resistance; awnless, nonshattering panicles; dormancy; and good panicle weight. Panicle weight was measured by dividing the total grain weight after removing the chaff by panicle length. We called that ratio C. Plants selected from the field by sight were tested for C factor and those with 0.1 C were judged panicle weight types. Of 980 selected plants, 522 had C 0.1. C is a desirable selection criterion for high yield in segregating generations of deep water crosses. C is 0.06 for deep water Nagaribao and 0.15 for high yielding variety Pankaj. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

TEMPERATURE TOLERANCE

Evaluating rices for cold tolerance

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Low temperatures are a major constraint to rice production in the hill region of India, where they adversely affect spring-sown upland rice at germination and early seedling growth, and transplanted rice

during ripening. We screened rices for low temperature tolerance in three experiments.

In the first, 135 varieties from different rice growing regions of the world, including some local hill collections, were evaluated for germination and seedling vigor in the spring of 1981 and 1982. On 2 Mar, 50 seeds of each variety were sown in 2 rows at 2-cm depth. The first seedlings emerged 18 d after sowing. L 62G,

Heug Jodo, Jodo, Heugdo, IRAT102, Khonorullo, K78-28, Daegaldo, Mujudo, and L 62-2A had more than 75% germination at an average 11°C field temperature. Sixty more genotypes emerged at 13°C and the rest emerged when the average temperature rose to 15°C in the first week of Apr. Of the early-emerging genotypes, all but IRAT102, K78-28, and L 62-2A had good seedling vigor at low temperatures and maintained their vigor